

PECULIARITIES OF COLORING OF BLENDED FABRICS FROM COTTON-POLYESTER FIBER USING CHITOSAN

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Abstract. this work highlights the problems arising in the process of dyeing mixed fiber fabrics and the application of *Apis mellefera* chitosan to reduce the consumption of consumables.

Key word: cotton, polyester (PE) fibers, mixed fiber, chitosan, disperse dye.

Аннотация. в данной работе освещены проблемы, возникающие в процессе крашения тканей из смесовых волокон и применения хитозана *Apis mellefera* для снижения расхода расходных материалов.

Ключевые слова: хлопок, полиэфирные (ПЭ) волокна, смесовое волокно, хитозан, дисперсный краситель.

The textile industry produces fabrics from various types of fibers of both natural and chemical origin. In the group of natural fibers, the most important are cotton, linen, and wool. Of synthetic materials, polyester (PEF), polyamide (PA) fibers are most widely used in textile and clothing industries. The most promising artificial fibers are viscose and acetate [1]. Polyester fibers (lavsan, tesil, terylene, dacron) are produced on the basis of polyethylene terephthalate:

Fig1. Polyethylene terephthalate (dacron).

Along with cellulose fibers, polyester (PE) fibers (Fig. 1) are the main textile raw materials in the world practice. In the production of many types of clothing, they are out of competition. Polyester fibers have high elasticity, light and heat resistance, and in terms of strength and abrasion resistance are inferior only to polyamide fibers. The disadvantages of polyester fibers include extremely low hygroscopicity, high electrification and degree of crystallinity. This makes it difficult to dye them, which, as a rule, is carried out at temperatures of the order of 130 ° C on pressure equipment. However, a new generation of polyester fibers is currently being produced that can be dyed at temperatures below 100°C, which solves the problems of coloring fabrics from a mixture of polyester and natural fibers. Polyester fibers are resistant to high temperatures and chemicals. They soften at 230–240°C and are resistant to dilute solutions of acids, alkalis, oxidizing agents, and reducing agents. Only concentrated mineral (sulphuric, nitric) and some organic acids, as well as concentrated alkali solutions (NaOH 40%) are capable of destroying the fiber.

One of the important trends in improving the range of polyester fiber fabrics is the use of textured multifilament yarns. Products from them have quite good hygienic and operational properties. Cotton fabrics are made from natural cellulose fiber - cotton. Cotton fiber for 95 - 96% consists of a natural polymer - cellulose [2]. Dyeing is understood as a physicochemical process of interaction of a fibrous material with dyes, in which the product acquires a uniform color that is resistant to various external influences.

According to their chemical structure, disperse dyes are polar organic compounds, slightly soluble in water. Since their molecules do not contain sulfo- and carboxyl groups ($-\text{NH}_2$, $-\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{OH})_2$, $-\text{OH}$, $-\text{OCH}_3$, etc.), they do not dissociate into ions in aqueous solutions, therefore they do not carry a charge. The solubility of dyes increases at temperatures above 80°C and in the presence of surfactants. Disperse dyes are widely used in the dyeing and printing of textile materials made of acetate, polyamide and polyester fibers exhibiting thermoplastic properties. Therefore, at present, special attention is paid to the creation of dyes that have an affinity for both chemical and natural fibers. Pigments meet these requirements. In addition, cotton-polyester fabrics can be printed using thermal transfer printing. In the process of dyeing polyester fibers, organic substances are used as intensifiers: phenols, chlorobenzene, benzoic and salicylic acids. The intensifier contributes to the dissolution of the dye, forms a complex with it, which more easily penetrates into the structure of the material, acting as a dye carrier from the solution to the fiber. In addition, the intensifier causes the fiber to swell, loosens and plasticizes it, increasing the number of available active groups on which the dye can be fixed. However, it should be borne in mind that intensifiers, as a rule, are toxic substances and reduce the light fastness of colors [3].

Therefore, we use natural local raw chitosan as an intensifier in the dyeing process of cotton-polyester blended fabric. This polymer dissolves in slightly acidic solutions, is non-toxic, and has a bactericidal effect. Chitin is a natural renewable product contained in the shells of crustaceans (shrimps, crayfish, etc.), insects, the number of which is measured in billions. Chitin is the second most common polysaccharide (after cellulose) in nature [4].

Fig 2. The process of dyeing cotton polyester fabric with chitosan.

In solution, the chitosan molecule acquires a positive charge due to the amino group, while fibers and most dyes in solution have a negative potential. Thus, in the presence of chitosan, dyes of one class will accumulate on the surface, forming a strong thin colored film (Fig. 2) [5].

Table 1.

The influence of the intensifier - chitosan on color quality indicators Intensifiers.

Intensifiers	100% polyester	100% cotton	cotton/PE
	Color intensity, K/S		
Apis mellifera chitosan of the dead bee	35	35	35.2
Bombyx mori mulberry silkworm boll chitosan	32	32	32.5
—	25	25	26

As can be seen from Table 1, the degree of binding of the dye to the fiber is higher in solutions with added chitosan. This is explained by the fixation of dyes on the chitosan film

with an amorphous structure. In turn, the chitosan film is attached to the fiber due to adhesion and intermolecular bonds.

In this work, the effect of chitosan on the process of dyeing mixed cotton-polyester fibers with disperse dyes was studied. The amino groups of chitosan react with the dye to form covalent bonds.

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